

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT SKILLS OF PUBLIC SCHOOL HEADS, COMPETENCE AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS, AND SCHOOL ACADEMIC READINESS IN CLUSTER 4 DIVISION OF CALAMBA CITY

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ABSTRACT

The primary goal of this study was to determine the correlation between the strategic managerial skills of school heads, teacher competence, and the academic readiness of public schools. It was conducted in the Cluster 4 District of the Division of Calamba City. The study employed a quantitative research design that utilized the descriptive correlational approach. Stratified random sampling was implemented. The study adopted a questionnaire from Melo's (2021) research to evaluate the strategic management skills of the school heads. Moreover, the study utilized a standardized monitoring/assessment tool from the DepEd to assess the level of competence of public school teachers and the level of academic readiness of schools. Furthermore, the data collected were handed accordingly and subjected to different statistical treatments using frequency count, simple mean, percentage, T-Test, and Pearson Product Moment-Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r). The results revealed that: School heads of Cluster 4 highly manifested their strategic management skills while the level of teaching competence of the public school teachers in Cluster 4 District was highly observable in terms of the given domains of the PPST 2023. Moreover, the level of academic readiness of the public schools were highly observed. Furthermore, based on the result there were significant correlations between the strategical management skills and the teaching competence in the given significant indicators. And lastly, there were significant correlations between strategic management skills of school heads towards academic readiness of public schools. In line with the findings, recommendations were given for school heads, teachers and schools for better improvement.

Keywords: *strategic management skills, competence, academic readiness, correlation, significant impact*

INTRODUCTION

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are designed to eradicate poverty, safeguard the planet, and foster prosperity on a global scale by the year 2030. One of the main objectives of the SDGs is to provide quality education and promote literacy worldwide. Education plays a crucial role in determining a country's level of development by producing a more knowledgeable and skilled workforce. However, the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines remains deeply concerned about the current state of basic education in the country despite numerous reforms. Effective school management is important for improving education quality. School leaders play a big role in the education system. By improving their management skills, they can become more effective and enhance education quality. These skills help them support teachers and create better schools.

In the Philippines, school leaders have a crucial role in improving school performance as mandated by Republic Act No. 9155. They work with teachers and learning facilitators to ensure the delivery of quality education and have the authority to direct teachers and students. However, there is a lack of research on how school heads' management skills impact teachers' competence and the academic readiness of public schools in the country. This is a significant concern given that educators play a vital role in shaping the curriculum and empowering students to acquire knowledge and skills. Previous studies have shown that the quality of education depends on the qualifications and competence of teachers.

Teaching is impactful as it shapes the future generation, but it comes with challenges. Teachers juggle various responsibilities, including education, behavior management, and completing administrative tasks. Schools need to evaluate and ensure accountability for student learning. When they reopen, they must assess student achievement to help those who fell behind. However, there may be equity disparities between those with access to distance learning and those without. Schools need to modify their assessment systems accordingly. Teachers have made great sacrifices to ensure quality education during the pandemic.

This study aimed to ascertain the correlation between the strategic managerial skills of school principals, teacher proficiency, and the academic readiness of seven elementary schools within Cluster 4 District, Division of Calamba City. Overall, the study aimed to analyze how the strategic management skills of school heads impact teacher competence and academic readiness.

Research Questions

This study determined and analyzed the level and impact of strategic management skills of public school heads, competence among public school teachers, and school academic readiness in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City. This research specifically wants to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of strategic management skills of the school heads in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City as assessed by teachers and school heads itself in terms of:
 - 1.1. Technical skills,
 - 1.2. Human skills,
 - 1.3. Conceptual skills,
 - 1.4. Communication skills, and
 - 1.5. Supervisory skills?
2. What is the level of competence of the public school teachers in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers itself in terms of:
 - 2.1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy,
 - 2.2. Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners,
 - 2.3. Curriculum Planning & Assessment and Reporting, and
 - 2.4. Personal Growth and Professional Development?
3. What is the level of academic readiness of public schools in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. Classroom Layout and Structure,
 - 3.2. Learning Resources,
 - 3.3. Teacher Support, and
 - 3.4. Curriculum and Learning?
4. Is there any significant difference between the assessment of the school heads and teachers as to strategic management skills, teaching competence and academic readiness of public schools in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City?
5. Is there any significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and teaching competence of the public-school teachers in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City?
6. Is there any significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and academic readiness of public schools in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what program/project may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative Research with Descriptive Correlational Research was used in this study to test the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. This design is appropriate for the study since it determines the relationship between the strategic management skills of each school head and the teaching competence of the different public-school teachers and the relationship between the strategic management skills of each school head and the academic readiness of their schools.

Participants

Stratified random sampling was employed in this study, which, according to Lauren Thomas (2020), is a randomly selected subset of a population. Each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected in this sampling method. This simple probability sampling technique involved a single random selection, reducing the risk of research fallacies like selection bias and sampling bias. Research conducted on this sample has high internal and external validity.

The research population was the Cluster 4 District, Division of Calamba, composed of school heads and teachers. With School Year 2022-2023, the Cluster 4 District consists of seven (7) school heads and one hundred ninety-four (194) permanent teaching forces. With the use of stratified random sampling, based on a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level using G power, 140 public school teachers out of the 194 total designated permanent teachers and 7 school heads in Cluster 4 District, Division of Calamba City were the final respondents of this study.

Instruments of the Study

Adopted survey questionnaires served as the chief instrument in gathering the data. The success of a thesis relies on the thorough selection and effective utilization of research instruments. It refers to the tools, techniques, and methodologies employed by researchers to collect, analyze, and interpret data. These instruments are crucial in ensuring the validity, reliability, and credibility of the research findings.

An adopted research instrument from the study of Melo (2021) will be used as a survey questionnaire in the first part of the questionnaire, which was all about the strategic managerial skills of school heads in terms of technical, human, conceptual, communication, and supervisory skills. It contains 25 items, with 5 items for each sub-variable. It also uses a scale of verbal interpretation of 4 as very high (VH), 3 as high (H), 2 as low (L), and 1 as very low (VL).

For the second part of the questionnaire, which was all about the competence of public-school teachers in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum planning and assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development, the researcher used a standardized

tool from the Department of Education, which is Professional Standards for Teachers for the school year 2023-2024, aligned with the updated tool in DM 008, S. 2023. It uses a scale of verbal interpretation of 4 as highly competent (HC), 3 as competent (C), 2 as slightly competent (SC), and 1 as not competent (NC).

And in the last part of the questionnaire, the academic readiness of public schools, the researcher will use a combined standardized tool from DepEd that is based on indicators in the School Safety Assessment Tool [SSAT]: classroom layout and structure, learning resources, and teacher support, and an indicator in the School Based Management (SBM) Tool, which is Curriculum and Learning. It uses a scale of verbal interpretation of 4 as very ready (VR), 3 as ready (R), 2 as slightly ready (SR), and 1 as not ready (NR).

Overall, the researcher used three (3) parts for the survey questionnaire in all variables of this study, which contains a total of fifty-one (51) questions that will both be assessed by the school heads and the teachers as respondents to this study.

Procedure

After the revision of the instruments, the researcher will see the Dean of Graduate Studies' approval to administer the questionnaires. Then, the researcher prepared a letter addressed to the school division superintendent and school heads asking for permission to conduct the study. The researcher personally endorsed the letter to the school heads for the dissemination of the questionnaire to the respondents through google form. After obtaining permission to conduct this study, the researcher will collect all required documentation to document, support, and formalize all phases. The researcher collected all the data online, logged it, and tallied it.

The statistician receives all the obtained data and applies statistical treatment to it. Their scores are gathered and evaluated once more to determine whether any differences have emerged. And then finally, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the results for the much-needed findings pertinent to the study. Ethical Considerations

RESULTS

This study, in general, intends to describe and assess the correlation between the strategic management skills of school heads, the competence of public school teachers, and the academic readiness of each school. The statements were scrutinized for specific questions to yield desired outcomes relative to the problem being studied.

Overall, it presents the tabular results of the summarized data, along with an analysis and interpretation that align with the statement objectives. The following data was collected for the age profile of the students:

Table 1.1***Level of Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Technical Skills***

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School Head.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Provided appropriate training to teachers for professional growth and development.	4.00	VH	3.34	VH	3.67	VH
Review our school performance vis-à-vis, mission and goals of the school.	4.00	VH	3.31	VH	3.66	VH
Use the appropriate monitoring and evaluation tools to assess the teachers.	4.00	VH	3.39	VH	3.70	VH
Allocate funds for the improvement of the school and to provide the needs of the teachers for teaching and learning.	4.00	VH	3.41	VH	3.70	VH
Provide technical assistance to teachers to improve teaching performance.	4.00	VH	3.42	VH	3.71	VH
General Assessment	4.00	VH	3.38	VH	3.69	VH

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High (VH) 2.50-3.24 High (H) 1.75-2.49 Low (L) 1.00-1.74 Very Low (VL)

The level of strategic management skills of the school heads as assessed by teachers and school heads in terms of Technical Skills was Very High as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.69 in table 1.1. The school head provide technical assistance to teachers to improve teaching performance which yielded the highest mean score of 3.71 and was interpreted as Very High. On the other hand, the school head review our school performance vis-à-vis, mission and goals of the school received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.66 and interpreted as Very High.

It implies that the school heads of Cluster 4 District, in terms of technical fields, have a high level of expertise and are fulfilling their job responsibilities effectively. Thus, the school head always provides technical assistance, or what we call TA, to each teacher every month as part of their monitoring activity. That is why it has the highest mean, because it is highly manifested. The lowest mean was obtained for reviewing school mission and goals because they are not specifically visible, but they should align with school mission and goals.

The main tasks that necessitate technical expertise include assessing and modifying teacher training programs, assisting teachers in identifying teaching and learning challenges, allocating funds effectively, and constructing quality yet achievable goals and objectives for the school. It is highly evident that when the principal's involvement is present, school activities and programs and even the teacher's performance in the learning process take place effectively and efficiently.

In line with this, according to Ramadan (2017) emphasized that the purpose of the school head's supervision is to develop teachers' professional abilities in fulfilling their

professional duties, thereby ensuring that teacher performance in the learning process is both optimal and competent.

Therefore, in order to empower teachers to carry out their tasks and obligations, principals not only allow teachers to do it themselves, but they also need to provide a positive example for teachers to follow. Because of this, it is essential for principals to possess expertise in technical matters.

Table 1.2
Level of Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Human Skills

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School Head.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Can create and motivate a healthy school culture for continual improvement in quality education.	4.00	VH	3.34	VH	3.67	VH
Can work as a team with other individuals in the school system to achieve set goals.	4.00	VH	3.46	VH	3.73	VH
Engage stakeholders in decision-making for the effective implementation of the programs and projects.	4.00	VH	3.44	VH	3.72	VH
Actively and personally guide specific initiatives to improve pupil's achievement.	4.00	VH	3.41	VH	3.71	VH
Create and motivate a healthy school culture for continual improvement in quality education.	4.00	VH	3.42	VH	3.71	VH
General Assessment	4.00	VH	3.41	VH	3.71	VH

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High (VH) 2.50-3.24 High (H) 1.75-2.49 Low (L) 1.00-1.74 Very Low (VL)

The level of strategic management skills of the school heads as assessed by teachers and school heads in terms of Human Skills was Very High as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.71 in table 1.2. The school head can work as a team with other individuals in the school system to achieve the set goals which yielded the highest mean score of 3.73 and was interpreted as Very High. On the other hand, the school head can create and motivate a healthy school culture for continual improvement in quality education indicator received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.67 and interpreted as Very High.

It implies that, in terms of human skills, the school heads of Cluster 4 District highly displayed their humanitarian characteristics as leaders. The indicator that the school head can work as a team or build a stronger team within his or her subordinates received the highest mean. This is because professionals in the field of education work well together when they have shared and valued goals, especially if their school head knows how to motivate, communicate, lead, and inspire them. On the other hand, the indicator that received the lowest mean is when school heads focus on creating and motivating a healthy school culture. This is because each school head is a unique individual with different characteristics and approaches to their work process. It got the lowest mean

because there are respondents who have a different view from the perspective of their school head, and it really has an effect on the scores gained.

To support these claims, the human skills that school heads acquire are aligned with the Human Relations Theory of Elton Mayo, which places emphasis on recognizing and appreciating the emotions, needs, and attitudes of employees in order to improve their motivation and productivity at work. Additionally, it fosters collaboration, employee engagement, and constructive connections between managers and employees.

Moreover, according to Day and Sammons (2016), the efficacy of an organization is contingent upon the leaders' human skills. Therefore, school head must foster human skills in order to achieve success in their leadership roles. Thus, fostering healthy relationships among subordinates by effectively using the human skills of school heads is important for promoting teamwork, creating a motivated environment, and enhancing work productivity.

Table 1.3
Level of Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Conceptual Skills

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School Head.....	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
Prepare strategic and long-term goals for the school and its personnel.	4.00	VH	3.42	VH	3.71	VH
Lead in conducting innovative projects which will help teachers and pupils in the effective implementation of the different learning modalities.	4.00	VH	3.43	VH	3.72	VH
Set the specific objectives and outcomes of the school activities.	4.00	VH	3.46	VH	3.73	VH
Craft school policies, rules and regulations.	4.00	VH	3.5	VH	3.75	VH
Encourage teachers to really give their best commitment to deliver instruction to the most important client in the department, the learners.	4.00	VH	3.52	VH	3.76	VH
General Assessment	4.00	VH	3.47	VH	3.74	VH

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High (VH) 2.50-3.24 High (H) 1.75-2.49 Low (L) 1.00-1.74 Very Low (VL)

The level of strategic management skills of the school heads as assessed by teachers and school heads in terms of Conceptual Skills was Very High as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.74 in table 1.3. The school head encouraged teachers to really give their best commitment to deliver instruction to the most important client in the department, the learners which yielded the highest mean score of 3.76 and was interpreted as Very High. On the other hand, the school head prepares strategic and long-term goals for the school and its personnel received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.71 and interpreted as Very High.

It indicates that the school heads in Cluster 4 District greatly strengthen their conceptual skills as school leaders. The indicator that the head of the school encourages teachers to give their all has reached its highest mean for a reason: school heads are more capable of inspiring and motivating their teachers to give their all, and most importantly, they recognize the value of every student in the school that they understand the interdependence of various organizational roles, where changes in one component inevitably impact other sections. However, the indicator that aims to develop strategic and long-term goals for the school and its staff achieved the lowest mean because most targets and goals are achieved for short-term rather than long-term processes.

School heads must possess and refine these skills in order to enhance their ability to achieve improved outcomes in the teaching and learning process and to effectively support programs and decision-making in school. Iskandar (2017) asserts that conceptual skills are essential for principals to effectively determine strategies, plan, formulate policies, and make judgments. Meanwhile, Pidarta asserts that conceptual skills are essential for comprehending and directing an organization. Hilal Mahmud defines conceptual talents as the managerial ability to formulate strategies and policies, innovate or develop something new, and make informed decisions (Mahmud, 2021).

Therefore, as a manager, the principal must possess strong conceptual skills in order to effectively guide the school organization towards professionalization and enhance the quality of instruction.

Table 1.4
Level of Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Communication Skills

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School Head.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Establish appropriate channels of communication that will help him to relate effectively with subordinates, and keep them properly informed of school plans, policies, and programs.	4.00	VH	3.35	VH	3.68	VH
Communicate information clearly without ambiguity	4.00	VH	3.37	VH	3.69	VH
Choose appropriate words to use in communicating with personnel.	4.00	VH	3.46	VH	3.73	VH
Design the medium he uses so that personnel receives the information without distortion.	4.00	VH	3.44	VH	3.72	VH
Use different platforms to communicate with the teachers and other stakeholders.	4.00	VH	3.39	VH	3.70	VH
General Assessment	4.00	VH	3.4	VH	3.70	VH

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High (VH) 2.50-3.24 High (H) 1.75-2.49 Low (L) 1.00-1.74 Very Low (VL)

The level of strategic management skills of the school heads as assessed by teachers and school heads in terms of Communication Skills was Very High as shown in

the general composite assessment of 3.70 in table 1.4. The school head choose appropriate words to use in communicating with personnel which yielded the highest mean score of 3.73 and was interpreted as Very High. On the other hand, the school head establish appropriate channels of communication that will help him to relate effectively with subordinates, and keep them properly informed of school plans, policies, and programs received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.68 and interpreted as Very High.

It implies that the school heads in Cluster 4 District positively possess their communication skills as school leaders. The indicator that attained the highest mean is that the school head chooses appropriate words to use in communicating with personnel. School heads nowadays strengthen their communication skills by attending seminars and trainings that greatly enhance those skills. Being a leader also means maintaining professionalism in action and through words. On the other hand, the indicator pertaining to the establishment of suitable communication channels by the school head to facilitate effective interaction with subordinates, and to ensure that they are adequately informed about school plans, policies, and programs, received the lowest mean. This is due to the fact that school heads often have multiple responsibilities that necessitate their absence from the school premises, compelling them to rely on online communication. However, not all teachers and school personnel prioritize the use of cellphones, resulting in delayed receipt of announcements.

But in general and most of the time, school heads are putting in their best effort to effectively communicate ideas and share information with their subordinates in a prompt and precise manner. They possess attentive ears for the staff members and communicate using concise and straightforward language. They adeptly engage with their stakeholders through several venues. Good communication skills are imperative for school heads to enhance presentation, motivation, enthusiasm, and conflict resolution in all school matters. This skill can help them get feedback and maintain healthy relationships with all school personnel.

Table 1.5
Level of Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Supervisory Skills

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School Head.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Supervise the teachers in the school to work as a team towards the achievement of school goals.	4.00	VH	3.4	VH	3.70	VH
Supervise instructional activities for the pupils.	4.00	VH	3.47	VH	3.74	VH
Provide solutions to the teaching problems of teachers.	4.00	VH	3.47	VH	3.74	VH
Guide and assist teachers to use innovative approaches to teaching in order to enhance instructional improvement.	4.00	VH	3.49	VH	3.75	VH

Work with teachers to improve the entire teaching and learning process in different learning modalities.	4.00	VH	3.41	VH	3.71	VH
General Assessment	4.00	VH	3.45	VH	3.73	VH

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High (VH) 2.50-3.24 High (H) 1.75-2.49 Low (L) 1.00-1.74 Very Low (VL)

The level of strategic management skills of the school heads as assessed by teachers and school heads in terms of Supervisory Skills was Very High as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.73 in table 1.5. The school head guide and assist teachers to use innovative approaches to teaching in order to enhance instructional improvement which yielded the highest mean score of 3.75 and was interpreted as Very High. On the other hand, the school head supervise the teachers in the school to work as a team towards the achievement of school goals received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.70 and interpreted as Very High.

It implies that the school administrators in Cluster 4 District actively nurture their skills to supervise as leaders of their schools. The indicator with the highest mean indicates that teachers received effective direction and support from their school administrators in order to successfully apply new techniques for improving education. On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest average suggests that certain teachers maybe experience working alone with some collaborative tasks that may affects their point of view with this indicator.

According to Tampan (2016), the duties of the supervisor include overseeing orders, motivating, directing, mentoring, and leading subordinates in the daily completion of school assignments. Indeed, according to Glickman (2020), as cited by Tampan (2020), the objective of school supervision is to assist educators in developing their own competencies so that they, the pupils, can accomplish professional objectives. In general, it is the duty of school administrators to oversee or scrutinize instructors while offering technical support to enhance the process of teaching and learning.

Table 2.1
Level of Competence of the Public School Teachers as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
The teachers.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas. (PPST 1.1.2)	4.00	HC	3.76	HC	3.88	HC
Used a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills. (PPST 1.4.2)	4.00	HC	3.73	HC	3.87	HC
Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills. (PPST 1.5.2)	4.00	HC	3.63	HC	3.82	HC

Displayed proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning. (PPST 1.6.2)	4.00	HC	3.72	HC	3.86	HC
General Assessment	4.00	HC	3.71	HC	3.86	HC

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Competent (HC) 2.50-3.24 Competent (C) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Competent (SL) 1.00-1.74 Not Competent (NC)

The level of competence of the public-school teachers as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy was Highly Competent as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.86 in table 2.1. The indicator which teachers applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas. (PPST 1.1.2) yielded the highest mean score of 3.88 and was interpreted as Highly Competent. On the other hand, the indicator that the teacher applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills. (PPST 1.5.2) received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.82 and interpreted as Highly Competent.

It implies that the competence of teachers in Cluster 4 District, in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy is highly visible. Teachers achieved the highest mean score in implementing content knowledge across all curriculum areas since they are teaching in their field of expertise or what we call their major ship and that personal qualities, such as enthusiasm and determination, also contribute to their teaching's efficacy and efficiency.

On the other hand, due to the teachers' heavy workload, which in reality is highly evident, utilizing a variety of teaching strategies to foster critical and inventive thinking as well as higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) received the lowest overall mean. The workloads that most of the public school teachers were experiencing, including classroom advisers or subject teachers, coordinating other special assignments, and managing paperwork, meant that teachers had limited time to consider and develop instructional strategies that foster critical and creative thinking, among other HOT skills.

Heaggart (2019) explained the importance of teachers' knowledge on the subject matter. He also emphasizes that teachers need broad knowledge and skills of curriculum teaching areas to help learners meet the standards and achieve high performance. To teach in accordance with modern demands, teachers must have a comprehensive and adaptable understanding of the subject matter to assist pupils in developing useful cognitive learning materials and address misconceptions.

Teachers must recognize the relevance of concepts to ordinary life and to other disciplines of learning. Moreover, the teachers in public schools often have to deal with large class sizes, heavy administrative workloads, and increasing pressure to meet performance targets.

As result, they may be overburdened with work, leading to high levels of stress and exhaustion (Rose & Sika 2019). When teachers are stressed and overworked, they may struggle to maintain their focus and motivation.

This can negatively impact their efficiency and their ability to provide quality education to their students (Hester, Bridges & Rollins, 2020). To which include the development of learners critical and creative thinking, as well as higher-order thinking skills.

And by that, Department of Education should implement measures to reduce workload of teachers or maybe eliminate extra work that is not involved in the teacher's teaching and learning process so that the teachers can focus on developing the areas to improve and develop of the learners. On the other hand, Cox (2019) highlighted some teaching techniques that can help develop HOTS. These include helping students determine what higher order thinking is, connecting concepts, teaching students to infer, encouraging teaching students to elaborate their answers and teaching question-answer-relationships.

Table 2.2
Level of Competence of the Public School Teachers as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
The teachers.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Established safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning through the consistent implementation of policies, guidelines and procedures. (PPST 2.1.2)	4.00	HC	3.76	HC	3.88	HC
Maintained learning environments that promote fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning. (PPST 2.2.2)	3.43	HC	3.73	HC	3.87	HC
Established a learner-centered culture by using teaching strategies that respond to their linguistic, cultural, socio- economic and religious backgrounds. (PPST 3.2.2)	4.00	HC	3.76	HC	3.74	HC
Adapted and used culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous groups. (PPST 3.5.2)	3.71	HC	3.79	HC	3.61	HC
General Assessment	3.79	HC	3.76	HC	3.78	HC

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Competent (HC) 2.50-3.24 Competent (C) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Competent (SL) 1.00-1.74 Not Competent (NC)

The level of competence of the public-school teachers as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of Learning Environment and Diversity of learners was Highly Competent as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.78 in table 2.2. The indicator which teachers established safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning through the consistent implementation of policies, guidelines and procedures. (PPST 2.1.2) yielded the highest mean score of 3.88 and was interpreted as

Highly Competent. On the other hand, the indicator the teacher adapted and used culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous groups. (PPST 3.5.2) received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.61 and interpreted as Highly Competent.

It implies that the competence of teachers in Cluster 4 District, in terms of learning environment and diversity of learners is highly observed. Teachers achieved the highest mean score in establishing safe and secure learning environment since they are the main responsible and controller of their classroom and also in shaping young minds. Part of their responsibility is establishing rules and regulations in their classroom that makes students feel safe and comfortable enable them to focus on learning. In line with this, throughout the academic year's orientation, instructors ensured that these rules and regulations were not overlooked in their establishment and enforcement, as they would serve as the cornerstone of a secure and safe learning environment within the classroom. On the contrary, it is the responsibility of educators to foster a classroom environment that promotes diversity, inclusion, and a sense of belonging for every student, regardless of cultural background. However, in practice, educators in public schools basically know this goal but unable to implement it in their daily lessons due to the necessity of discussing and ensuring that all expected learning competencies are met. And also, teachers doesn't have enough seminars and trainings on how to handle cultural differences of each learners.

To secure the learning environment for each learner, Watanabe-Crockett (2019), emphasizes that safe learning environments transform into comfortable learning environments that is why he cited different tips on how to implement a safe learning environment. Creating safe learning environment in the classroom is essential for serving the vast spectrum of student learning styles. By creating a positive and trusting classroom environment, teachers can provide their students the safety and support they need for academic, personal, and professional development. Moreover, in terms of diversity of learners through linguistic and cultural aspects, Department of Education through its program, Education for All supports all learners individualities to have a same quality of education regardless of any aspects. Along with that, The Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) Program of DepEd, aims to to improve the appropriateness and responsiveness of the curriculum; build the capacity of teachers, managers and concerned personnel; support the development of culturally appropriate learning resources and learning environment and strengthen the policy environment supportive of IPEd. It is, likewise, intended to address the learning needs of IP learners who lack access to basic education services. In addition, Calvo (2020), stated his reflection on a model of education aimed teachers and learners understand and be familiarized with the linguistic and cultural diversity. It highlights that learner's diversity should be considered a wealth, not a problem.

Table 2.3
Level of Competence of the Public School Teachers as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Curriculum Planning and Assessment and Reporting

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
The teachers.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Set achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies. (PPST 4.2.2)	3.43	HC	3.7	HC	3.57	HC
Used strategies for providing timely, accurate and constructive feedback to improve learner performance. (PPST 5.3.2)	4.00	HC	3.74	HC	3.87	HC
Utilized assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs. (PPST 5.5.2)	4.00	HC	3.73	HC	3.87	HC
General Assessment	3.81	HC	3.72	HC	3.77	HC

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Competent (HC) 2.50-3.24 Competent (C) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Competent (SL) 1.00-1.74 Not Competent (NC)

The level of competence of the public-school teachers as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of Curriculum Planning and Assessment and Reporting was Highly Competent as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.77 in table 2.3. The two indicators that gained the highest mean score of 3.87 and was interpreted as Highly Competent are the teachers' used strategies for providing timely, accurate and constructive feedback to improve learner performance. (PPST 5.3.2) and they utilized assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs. (PPST 5.5.2). On the other hand, the indicator that teacher set achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies. (PPST 4.2.2) received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.57 and interpreted as Highly Competent.

It implies that teachers in Cluster 4 District, in terms of curriculum planning and assessment and reporting is highly proficient. Teachers achieved the highest mean score in using feedback strategies to improve learner performance and utilizing assessment data to inform the modification of practices and program. Giving effective feedback to students is central to their learning. Feedback assists all students in understanding the subject matter and provides clear guidance on how to improve their learning procedure. Simple feedback can help students gain confidence, self-awareness, and enthusiasm for what they are learning. Giving students relevant feedback can help them improve their academic or fieldwork performance. In line with this, teachers are well expert in implementing a range of practices and strategies that ensure effective feedback is given to each student.

Furthermore, teachers delivered classroom assessments regularly. It can be in formative or performance assessments. It is highly utilized to make better improvements. It is essential for teachers to see and understand that assessment is one of the integral

parts of the instruction process and as crucial for helping students learn. Teachers used assessment process and data meaningfully, and because of that they do better in delivering instructional practices effectively.

On the other hand, the indicator that got the lowest mean score is teachers set achievable and appropriate learning outcomes, it is because the public schools have its own curriculum that learning competencies are standardized for every student. It is apparent that a classroom contains a heterogeneous group of students with varying degrees of intelligence, and it is not optimal to construct and implement a single learning outcome for each subject. This factor contributed to the indicator having the lowest mean value.

Kumar (2025) emphasized the importance of feedback on student development. In his article, he stated that feedback is an essential component of the educational system. It can be incorporated to enhance teaching and learning techniques since it has an immediate impact on the process of acquiring knowledge and has a direct impact on both teaching and learning. University of South Carolina (n.d) expressed that Teachers have the distinct responsibility to nurture a student's learning and to provide feedback in such a manner that the student does not leave the classroom feeling defeated. When feedback is predominately negative, studies have shown that it can discourage student effort and achievement. To better improve and enhance giving of feedback in classroom set up, Open Colleges (2022), recommended strategies and techniques on how to give effective feedback that will leave your students with the feeling they can conquer the world. In this article it highlighted the concept "feedback sandwich" for efficient and effective giving of feedback to the students, it means Compliment, Correct, Compliment.

Assessment is making sure if the students mastered the lessons being taught that day. It can be in form of formative or performance assessment. Formative assessment serves two purposes: it aids students in identifying their own learning difficulties and facilitates the intervention of alternative remedial strategies; and it helps teachers in identifying the specific challenges students face in subject matter content and predicting the outcome of summative assessments.

And lastly, learning outcomes must be simply and clearly described. To better construct learning outcomes, teachers must understand the Blooms Taxonomy framework that most of the teacher applied in their teaching process. An online resource, Academic Programmes Quality & Resources Unit (n.d.), discusses the procedures in developing effective learning outcomes. Popenic, S., & Milla, V. (2019), present succinct and practical information about learning outcomes, their function and some practical strategies for how to start thinking about and writing them.

Table 2.4***Level of Competence of the Public School Teachers as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development***

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
The teachers.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Build relationships with parents/ guardians and the wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process. (PPST 6.2.2)	3.43	HC	3.69	HC	3.57	HC
Participated in professional networks to share knowledge and to enhance practice. (PPST 7.3.2)	3.71	HC	3.74	HC	3.73	HC
Developed a personal improvement plan based on reflection of one's practice and ongoing professional learning. (PPST 7.4.2)	3.43	HC	3.69	HC	3.55	HC
General Assessment	3.52	HC	3.7	HC	3.61	HC

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Competent (HC) 2.50-3.24 Competent (C) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Competent (SL) 1.00-1.74 Not Competent (NC)

The level of competence of the public school teachers as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development was Highly Competent as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.61 in table 2.4. The indicator which teachers participated in professional networks to share knowledge and to enhance practice. (PPST 7.3.2) yielded the highest mean score of 3.73 and was interpreted as Highly Competent. On the other hand, the indicator that teacher developed a personal improvement plan based on reflection of one's practice and ongoing professional learning. (PPST 7.4.2) received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.55 and interpreted as Highly Competent.

It implies that teachers in Cluster 4 District, in terms of personal growth and professional development is highly proficient. Teachers achieved the highest mean score in participating in professional networks, for a reason that teachers nowadays are expected to value personal growth and professional development and exhibit high personal regard for the profession because it helps them grow and develop in their teaching career and most importantly it can as mean of promotion. Teachers actively engage in collaborative learning with the professional community and other stakeholders for mutual growth and advancement. Educators must establish a professional learning network in order to grow their field of influence beyond the confines of the classroom, exchange curricula, and gain access to innovative teaching techniques.

On the other hand, developing a personal improvement plan got the lowest mean score since most of the teachers were not aware of its importance. In reality, teachers are only familiar with self-assessment, or what we call nowadays E-SSAT, and disregard the importance of constructing a personal improvement plan after the self-assessment. It is important for a teacher to construct a plan that integrates interventions and activities that have the potential to augment their professional development and examine how these

interventions or activities can assist in addressing their area of greatest need for improvement and/or further enhance their proficiency in the domain where they are at their highest level as an educator.

Reflecting on Guskey’s (2020) assertion regarding professionals, including teachers, who need to stay informed of current trends and techniques related to the field of education. It is to better enhance their capabilities as a person and efficiency as a teacher. Educators engage in an endless journey in which they seek out new strategies and concepts to enhance their own abilities and acquire fresh knowledge, all with the goal of ensuring the success of their students. Personal growth and professional development is a tool that allows teachers to become or remain effective in the classroom. Hein (as cited in Beavers, n.d) supported this idea: “Growth and improvement of any educational institution, teacher professional development becomes a milestone in teachers’ continuum of life-long learning and career progression”.

Table 3.1
Level of Academic Readiness of the Public School as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Classroom Layout and Structure

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Follows recommended strategies as cited in DOLE Department Order No. 224_221 Guidelines on Ventilation for Workplaces and public Transport to Prevent and Control the spread of COVID.	3.86	VR	3.37	VR	3.62	VR
Is well-cleaned, prepared, and orderly with smart ambiance, stimulating for all learners.	3.43	VR	3.42	VR	3.43	VR
Has appropriate instructional rooms and facilities for the use of all learners with appropriate tools and with sufficient designated tables and chairs.	4.00	VR	3.41	VR	3.71	VR
General Assessment	3.76	VR	3.40	VR	3.58	VR

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Ready (VR) 2.50-3.24 Ready (R) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Ready (SR) 1.00-1.74 Not Ready (NR)

The level of academic readiness of the public school in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of Classroom Layout and Structure was Very Ready as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.58 in table 3.1. The indicator which schools has appropriate instructional rooms and facilities for the use of all learners with appropriate tools and with sufficient designated tables and chairs yielded the highest mean score of 3.71 and was interpreted as Very Ready. On the other hand, the indicator that school is well-cleaned, prepared, and orderly with smart ambiance, stimulating for all learners received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.43 and interpreted as Very Ready.

It implies that the academic readiness of public school in Cluster 4 District, in terms of classroom layout and structure is very ready. Schools has appropriate instructional rooms and facilities for the use of all learners achieved the highest mean score. This was made possible by the Local Government Unit, which, in collaboration with the Department of Education, implemented projects to gradually add classroom equipment, including chairs and tables, constructing new school buildings, which facilitate the teaching and learning process. One of the objectives of Mayor Ross Rizal in the City of Calamba is to furnish all public schools with adequate classroom equipment so that every student may feel safe and at ease in their second home, the schools. It is said that a classroom that has a well-defined physical arrangement, complete classroom equipment and resources, will promote a positive learning environment to teachers and students. On the other hand, the indicator school is well cleaned, prepared and orderly got the lowest mean because of different reasons, it could be the school has limited funding source in MOOE, high student-to-teacher ratio that cause the teachers to find it challenging to manage and organize classrooms effectively, which can contribute to a lack of cleanliness and orderliness, and shortage of support staff, such as school utilities or maintenance personnel, who are responsible for cleaning and organizing classrooms.

To support the above-mentioned statements, in the 1st State of the City Address of Mayor Ross Rizal (July 2023), he reported the urgent progress of the Local Government Unit of Calamba through the programs and projects of his political agenda tagged 'Ramdam na Reporma'. As part of his major accomplishments in the education sector, he highlighted the provision of 104,743 sets of learner kits with shirt uniforms to all public-school learners, ICT equipment, furniture, office and school supplies. He also reported the building of the proposed 4-storey, 16-classroom school buildings in different barangays in the community that supports the quality education that the Department of Education mandated. In addition, in the article of Abu Hurayra (2023), he highlighted the growing significance of educational apparatus in the present time, noting its pivotal function in augmenting the scholastic experience of pupils. This equipment has become more interactive, engaging, and effective at fostering a conducive learning environment.

On the other hand, the cited issues, and challenges that a public school are now facing can cause negative impact on the teaching and learning process most especially on delivery the quality education for the students. Janelle Cox (2019) stated that maintaining a clean and tidy classroom environment is important. In an article of Carol Burris, she states that "students and teachers need clean, roomy, well-ventilated and well-lit spaces for teaching and learning." Addressing these issues often requires a collaborative effort involving school administrators, government authorities, community members, and other stakeholders to prioritize and allocate resources towards maintaining clean and organized learning spaces.

Table 3.2***Level of Academic Readiness of the Public School as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Learning Resources***

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Secures sufficient supply of learning resources needed for the teaching-learning process.	3.43	VR	3.31	VR	3.37	VR
Ensures that all their teachers have the Teacher's Guide/ Teacher's Manual on specific grade levels and learning areas.	3.86	VR	3.49	VR	3.68	VR
Develops activity-based materials for mastery of learning delivered in teaching and learning process.	4.00	VR	3.41	VR	3.71	VR
General Assessment	3.76	VR	3.4	VR	3.58	VR

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Ready (VR) 2.50-3.24 Ready (R) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Ready (SR) 1.00-1.74 Not Ready (NR)

The level of academic readiness of the public school in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of Learning Resources was Very Ready as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.58 in table 3.2. The indicator which schools develops activity-based materials for mastery of learning delivered in teaching and learning process yielded the highest mean score of 3.71 and was interpreted as Very Ready. On the other hand, the indicator that school secures sufficient supply of learning resources needed for the teaching-learning process received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.37 and interpreted as Very Ready.

It implies that the academic readiness of public school in Cluster 4 District, in terms of learning resources is very ready. Schools develops activity-based materials for mastery of learning delivered in teaching and learning process achieved the highest mean score since part of the programs and projects of each school is to construct learning materials that they can used in teaching and learning process to secure the mastery of learning for every competency. It could be in differentiated activities such as peer, group, and class activities that intervention materials. The key is to design activities that actively engage students, promote critical thinking, and align with the learning objectives of the subject. The choice of activity-based materials should be based on the specific needs, interests, and developmental level of the students. On the other hand, the indicator school secures sufficient supplies of learning resources got the lowest mean score because in reality it has been the issues and challenges that each public school experienced. Learning resources has its own budget from DepEd that allocates on the production of learners' materials and teacher's materials that can be use in teaching and learning process. Along with, outdated or inaccurate content that can lead to confusion and misinformation among students and hinder their ability to acquire accurate and up-to-date knowledge.

Table 3.3***Level of Academic Readiness of the Public School as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Teacher Support***

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Provides an appropriate learning and development support plan in the delivery of better-quality basic education services.	4.00	VR	3.44	VR	3.72	VR
Delivers of School-Based Learning Action Cells (LAC) sessions to ensure that the ability of teachers to deliver relevant teaching and learning strategies and ensure continuity of learning.	3.86	VR	3.53	VR	3.70	VR
Conducts coaching, mentoring, and training for enhancement of the teaching process.	4.00	VR	3.45	VR	3.73	VR
General Assessment	3.95	VR	3.47	VR	3.71	VR

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Ready (VR) 2.50-3.24 Ready (R) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Ready (SR) 1.00-1.74 Not Ready (NR)

The level of academic readiness of the public school in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of teacher support was Very Ready as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.71 in table 3.3. The indicator which schools conducts coaching, mentoring, and training for enhancement of the teaching process yielded the highest mean score of 3.73 and was interpreted as Very Ready. On the other hand, the indicator that school delivers a School-Based Learning Action Cells (LAC) sessions to ensure that the ability of teachers to deliver relevant teaching and learning strategies and ensure continuity of learning received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.70 and interpreted as Very Ready.

It implies that the academic readiness of public school in Cluster 4 District, in terms of teacher support is very ready. The indicator that schools implement coaching, mentoring, and training received the highest mean score since each school conducts a self-assessment prior to the start of the academic year to identify the areas in which each teacher requires improvement through participation in a coaching and mentoring program. This program was organized for the duration of the academic year, with predetermined topics for the resource speaker to discuss.

On the other hand, school delivering and conducting SLAC session got the lowest score mean since SLAC is a mandatory program for every public school, some of them are unable to conduct it on time because of some challenges a school experienced including lack of time since the DepEd mandated time on task policy that all the extra-curricular and extra-curriculum activities of a school must conduct after class schedule. Finding dedicated time for SLAC sessions can be difficult, leading to rushed or infrequent meetings that may not effectively address the intended goals. In addition, lack of facilitation skills were not all facilitators or resource speaker may not possess the necessary skills to guide productive discussions because of their field of expertise.

And lastly, insufficient resources and support where it plays a vital role in the success of SLAC sessions. Lack of access to relevant learning materials, research-based resources, or ongoing support from school administrators can hinder the effectiveness of the school programs and projects.

Having strong foundation of teacher support can contribute to the preparation and successful implementation of school programs in all areas. According to Koki (2019), quality teaching is essential if the mission of education is to be fulfilled. Mentoring can play a critical role in continually improving the professional knowledge and skills that teachers need to instruct and prepare students for the next century. However, to be effective, mentoring programs must be developed that take into account the complexity, process and function of the programs.

DepEd Order No. 35, s 2016 stating “The Learning Action Cell (LAC) as a K to 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning., which focuses on improving and enhancing teachers content knowledge, pedagogical skills, assessment strategies, and professional ethics to better deliver the quality education to one school.

Table 3.4
Level of Academic Readiness of the Public School as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Curriculum and Learning

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
Our School.....	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Identifies all types of learners of the school community and develops appropriate programs with support of learning materials for each type of learners.	3.86	VR	3.53	VR	3.70	VR
Implements localized curriculum and ensures more meaningful, and pleasurable desired learning outcomes.	4.00	VR	3.49	VR	3.75	VR
Develops methods and materials for developing creative thinking and problem solving.	3.43	VR	3.46	VR	3.45	VR
General Assessment	3.76	VR	3.50	VR	3.63	VR

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Ready (VR) 2.50-3.24 Ready (R) 1.75-2.49 Slightly Ready (SR) 1.00-1.74 Not Ready (NR)

The level of academic readiness of the public school in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of curriculum and learning was Very Ready as shown in the general composite assessment of 3.63 in Table 3.4. The indicator which implements localized curriculum and ensures more meaningful, and pleasurable desired learning outcomes yielded the highest mean score of 3.75 and was interpreted as Very Ready. On the other hand, the indicator that school develops methods and materials for developing creative thinking and problem solving received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.45 and interpreted as Very Ready.

It implies that the academic readiness of public school in Cluster 4 District, in terms of curriculum and learning is very ready. Schools implements localized curriculum achieved the highest mean score since it is essential feature of the K to 12 Curriculum by linking new content of lessons to the local experiences that are familiar to students to achieve more efficient and relevant learning for them. Schools with the help of the teachers and administrators plan, construct and establish their own modified local curriculum to accommodate the unique contexts of a particular locality.

On the other hand, schools develop methods and materials for developing creative thinking and problem solving received the lowest mean score since developing materials nowadays is not that easy task because of the different reasons that need to be considered such as lack of fundings, additional work for teachers, and many more. Schools may utilize contextualization and localization of curricula as strategies to improve students' academic achievement. By embracing and devoting their time to being innovative, proactive, and proficient in utilizing community resources, they can construct real-life experiences for students that link concepts to pertinent issues, thereby fostering the development of necessary skills and competencies. Moreover, they can assist students in becoming proficient in their chosen professions, as mandated by the K–12 programs.. Manuel (n.d.) asserts that curriculum developers may incorporate contextualization and localization as a prominent pedagogical approach to enhance students' academic achievements across various subject domains.

Table 4
Test of Significant Difference Between the assessment of the School Heads and Teachers as to Strategic Management Skills, Teaching Competence and Academic Readiness of Public Schools

Variables	T test	P value	Remarks	Decision
Technical Skills	15.483	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Human Skills	13.302	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Conceptual Skills	12.643	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Communication Skills	14.041	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Supervisory Skills	15.159	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	10.919	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	.203	.145	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Curriculum Planning and Assessment & Reporting	1.164	.276	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Personal Growth and Professional Development	1.327	.187	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Classroom Layout and Structure	5.206	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Learning Resources	5.158	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Teachers' Support	8.087	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Curriculum and Learning	3.804	.003	Significant	Reject t Ho

There was significant difference in the assessment of the school heads and teachers as to strategic management skills, teaching competence and academic readiness of public schools such as technical skills, human skills, conceptual skills, communication skills, supervisory skills, content knowledge and pedagogy, classroom

layout and structure, learning resources, teachers' support and curriculum and learning. Table 4 showed the probability values of .000, .000, .000, .000, .000, .000, .000, .000, .000, and .003 respectively are less than the level of significance at .05. thus reject the null hypothesis. On the other hand, there was no significant difference in the assessment of the school heads and teachers as to learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, and personal growth and professional development. The probability values are greater than the level of significance at .05. thus accept the null hypothesis, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference on the assessment of the school heads and teachers.

With the result, it implies that each person in the universe possesses a unique perspective on the things that comprise life. According to the online article by MH Theme (2023), an individual's perspective and understanding of a concept can shape their opinion, regardless of how others perceive it. Furthermore, this article highlights the different aspects that influence an individual's view, which include past experiences, educational attainment, personal values, cultural influences both internal and external, and current situations. There is a statistically significant difference in the assessments of the variables abovementioned between school heads and teachers in this study. However, there are no significant differences were found in the assessments of the other three domains with the competence of the teacher. This finding implies they share a common background, namely being involved in the field of education.

Table 5
Test of Significant Relationship between the Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads and Teaching Competence of the Public School Teachers

Strategic Mgt	Teaching Competence	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Technical Skills	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.171*	.038	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	.167*	.043	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum Planning and Assessment & Reporting	.139	.092	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.130	.117	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Human Skills	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.162*	.050	Significant	Reject Ho
	Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	.162*	.050	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum Planning and Assessment & Reporting	.182*	.028	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.094	.255	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Conceptual Skills	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.153	.064	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	.204*	.013	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum Planning and Assessment & Reporting	.178*	.031	Significant	Reject t Ho

Communication Skills	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.106	.201	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.098	.237	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	.162*	.050	Significant	Reject Ho
	Curriculum Planning and Assessment & Reporting	.153	.065	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Supervisory Skills	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.076	.358	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.190*	.021	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	.239**	.004	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum Planning and Assessment & Reporting	.296**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.137	.099	Not Significant	Accept Ho

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

There was significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and teaching competence of the public school teachers such as technical skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, technical skills and learning environment and diversity of learners, human skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, human skills and learning environment and diversity of learners, human skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, conceptual skills and learning environment and diversity of learners, conceptual skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, communication skills and learning environment and diversity of learners, supervisory skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, supervisory skills and learning environment and diversity of learners and supervisory skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting. Table 5 showed the probability values of .038, .043, .050, .050, .028, .013, .031, .050, .021, .004, and .000 respectively were less than the level of significance at .05. thus reject the null hypothesis, it can be concluded that there was significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and teaching competence of the public school teachers in the abovementioned areas.

On the other hand, there was no significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and teaching competence of the public school teachers in terms of technical skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, technical skills and personal growth and professional development, human skills and personal growth and professional development, conceptual skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, conceptual skills and personal growth and professional development, communication skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, communication skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, communication skills and personal growth and professional development, and supervisory skills, and personal growth and development. The probability values were greater than the level of significance at .05. thus accept the null hypothesis, it can be concluded that there was no significant

relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and teaching competence of the public school teachers in the abovementioned areas.

It was highly evident that the strategic management skills of school heads had a significant correlation to the variable of teaching competence which is learning environment and diversity of learners and somehow correlated to content knowledge and pedagogy and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting. Effective strategic management skills of the school head had the potential to significantly improved the teaching-learning environment of a school, which in turn can positively impact the school's internal and external environment, as per a study by Almutairi & Shraid (2021). The school head's management skills were critical for enhancing the quality of education, the competence of teacher and the performance of students, as highlighted by Malik & Akram (2020). These skills also played a vital role in creating an effective working climate for teaching and learning. The school climate includes norms, interactions between teachers and students, and the overall structure of the school, as explained by Aziz & Ahmad (2020). Thus, when the strategic management skills of school heads increased, there was an increased in the level of teaching competence of public school teachers. And when the strategic management skills of school heads decreased, it can affect the competence of the public school teachers.

It implies that the effectiveness of teachers in classrooms greatly depends on their dedication and classroom management skills, which should be assessed by principals with effective managerial skills (Naidoo 2019). Hence, to ensure the success of the school, principals should utilize their expertise and potential to achieve the desired educational institutional goals for both teachers and students (Mwesiga & Okendo 2018). Therefore, the role of a principal is crucial in creating a structure and subordinates who can work according to their respective responsibilities, which is possible if they carry out their managerial competencies properly (Hartati, Pepriyeni, & Suryana 2019).

Based on recent research by Patarusi (2017), it has been found that principals who possess strong managerial skills significantly enhance teacher performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that effective leadership and management by principals play a crucial role in improving the overall quality of education. Principals should provide ongoing supervision to create a supportive and encouraging environment for teachers to enhance their skills and capabilities. This approach would foster positive relationships among staff, encourage collaboration, and motivate all members to work towards achieving the school's objectives (Giami & Obiechina, 2019).

Table 6**Test of Significant Relationship between the Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads and Academic Readiness of Public School in Cluster 4 District Division of Calamba**

Strategic Mgt	Teaching Competence	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Technical Skills	Classroom Lay out	.371**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Learning Resources	.333**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Teacher's Support	.365**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum	.361**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Human Skills	Classroom Lay out	.303**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Learning Resources	.252**	.002	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Teacher's Support	.318**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum	.349**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Conceptual Skills	Classroom Lay out	.304**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Learning Resources	.283**	.001	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Teacher's Support	.329**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum	.300**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Communication Skills	Classroom Lay out	.322**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Learning Resources	.278**	.001	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Teacher's Support	.298**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum	.367**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
Supervisory Skills	Classroom Lay out	.352**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Learning Resources	.369**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Teacher's Support	.405**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho
	Curriculum	.382**	.000	Significant	Reject t Ho

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

There was significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and academic readiness of public schools in the new normal as shown in the probability values were all 0.000 which was less than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. It indicates that there is a substantial link between the strategic management skills of the school heads and academic readiness of public schools. This also indicated that the better the strategic management skills of the school heads, the more academic readiness of public schools. In addition, it can also imply that the higher the strategic management skills of the school heads the higher the level of academic readiness of public schools.

In the study of Giami & Obiechina (2019), school head management skills refer to the capacity to plan, oversee, organize, coordinate, control, make decisions, and start actions that will assist and support teachers in achieving the school goals and objectives. Regardless, managers are free to develop managerial skills that will aid in the achievement of school goals and objectives. In line with this, Abdurahman and Ormar (2021) highlight that for decades, educational officials worldwide have pushed to enhance school performance.

By that, school heads articulate a common purpose of establishing distributed leadership within a collaborative school climate. In the Philippines, Republic Act No.9155 mandates that public schools or clusters of schools must have a school head or principal who works closely with teachers and learning facilitators to deliver high-quality educational programs, projects, and services for better student outcomes.

By promoting a collaborative approach to school leadership, we can create an environment that enhances the quality of education and better prepares students for the future. Therefore, it is crucial for school leaders to continually develop and refine their managerial skills, enabling them to lead their schools with confidence toward achieving their goals and objectives.

The Proposed Program Attain Strong Bond for School Success

The program Project ASBSS: Attain Strong Bond for School Success is a strategic intervention on fostering healthy relationship between school head, teachers and school for the success of the school goals and objectives. This program was crafted based on the findings of this study and presented below:

School Programs	Objectives	Strategies / Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source of Funds	Success Indicators
Progress-In and Progress-Out	a. To monitor teaching staff's professional development	a. Progressive Wall: Allocate a place in the principal's	a. The monitoring of teacher's performance will be	Monitoring and Evaluating Team: School Head, and	The estimated cost for materials needed, transportation	a. Teachers' portfolio and result of RPMS evaluation.

of School	<p>t as basis for recognition of teachers who showed exemplary performances.</p> <p>b. Collaborate with schools who are recognized in the last year's Gawad Calambayani about the personnel or school's best practices as basis for annual improvement plan.</p>	<p>office, similar to a checklist, that shows teachers' accomplishments like quarterly classroom observation, progress of proposed plans and activities. The result of these accomplishments will be discussed with the head teachers. Quarterly report shall be provided as basis for recognition of exemplary teachers.</p> <p>b. Bench Marking: Conduct bench marking with schools who are recognized in the last year's Gawad Calambayani and have a re-echo for the personnel and staff of the school.</p>	<p>done whole year round by the school head and its evaluation shall be done quarterly together with the head teachers.</p> <p>b. Bench marking with other school will take place once every quarter, re-echo shall follow within the first week after the said bench marking.</p>	<p>Head Teachers</p> <p>Participants and benefactor: All teaching personnel</p> <p>Contributors: School head, head teachers and/or master teachers, and recognized personnel and staff in the last year's Gawad Calambayani from other school</p>	<p>on, and other miscellaneous will be from the combination of schools' local fund and MOOE.</p>	<p>b. Portfolio submission for Gawad Calambayani.</p> <p>c. Documentation and terminal report for benchmarking</p> <p>d. Documentation and terminal report of the re-echo</p>
TECH- ch- ers in the Making	<p>a. Promote verbal, nonverbal, and written communication skills between</p>	<p>a. Tech-Talk- Two: Inspired from a board game tic tac toe.</p>	<p>a. Quarter 2 and 4 of the present school year as these are</p>	<p>a. Head Teachers are responsible on the one-on-one</p>	<p>The estimated cost for the seminar-workshop will be</p>	<p>a. Documentation and terminal report on the conducted</p>

	teachers for classroom teaching.	<p>For tech, a seminar-workshop headed by ICT coordinator shall take place to share applications that can be used during classroom teaching. In this manner, teachers will have an option for attaining a higher grade in COT-RPMS objective 8.</p> <p>For talk, teachers must allocate time in explaining and demonstrating one application to students that should be manipulated by them.</p>	the only quarter where objective 8 is evaluated in COT-RPMS.	<p>feedback evaluation.</p> <p>Teachers are responsible in explaining and demonstrating of the application.</p> <p>Benefactor: Students</p>	funded by the MOOE.	<p>seminar-workshop.</p> <p>b. Documentation of the teachers during sharing and demonstration of the application.</p> <p>b. Students rating in performance task of the application.</p>
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The elementary schools of Cluster 4 in the Division of Calamba City may implement the following proposed programs in order to strengthen and improve the relationship between school heads, teachers, and the school. This document has the potential to function as a plan for them to develop their own educational programs that benefit all stakeholders, particularly the learners, who are the most vital clients of education. Lastly, it has the potential to facilitate benchmarking, which could be advantageous for other schools in the Division of Calamba as well as for educational institutions nationwide.

DISCUSSION

After an in-depth review of the data collected, the following are the study's findings, summarized in the following manner.

1. Level of Strategical Management Skills of School Heads in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City
 - 1.1. Technical Skills
It had a composite mean of 3.69 and was verbally interpreted as Very High.
 - 1.2. Human Skills
It had a composite mean of 3.71 and was verbally interpreted as Very High.
 - 1.3. Conceptual Skills
It had a composite mean of 3.71 and was verbally interpreted as Very High.
 - 1.4. Communication Skills
It had a composite mean of 3.70 and was verbally interpreted as Very High.
 - 1.5. Supervisory Skills
It had a composite mean of 3.73 and was verbally interpreted as Very High.
2. Competency Level of Public School Teachers in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City
 - 2.1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy
It obtained a 3.86 mean score and interpreted as Very Competent.
 - 2.2. Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners
It obtained a 3.78 mean score and interpreted as Very Competent.
 - 2.3. Curriculum Planning and Assessment & Reporting
It obtained a 3.77 mean score and interpreted as Very Competent.
 - 2.4. Personal Growth and Professional Development
It obtained a 3.61 mean score and interpreted as Very Competent.
3. Level of Academic Readiness of Public Schools in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City
 - 3.1. Classroom Layout and Structure
It obtained a 3.58 mean score and interpreted as Very Ready.
 - 3.2. Learning Resources
It obtained a 3.58 mean score and interpreted as Very Ready.
 - 3.3. Teacher Support
It obtained a 3.71 mean score and interpreted as Very Ready
 - 3.4. Curriculum and Learning
It obtained a 3.63 mean score and interpreted as Very Ready.
4. Test of Significant Difference between the assessment of the School Heads and Teachers as to Strategic Management Skills, Teaching Competence and Academic Readiness of Public Schools. There was significant difference on the assessment of the school heads and teachers as to strategic management skills, teaching competence and academic readiness of public schools such as technical skills, human skills, conceptual skills, communication skills, supervisory skills, content knowledge and pedagogy, classroom layout and structure, learning resources, teachers' support and curriculum and learning. The probability values were lesser than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. There was also no significant difference on the assessment of the school heads and teachers

as to learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, and personal growth and professional development. The probability values were greater than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

5. Test of Significant Relationship between the Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads and Competence of the Public School Teachers in Cluster 4 District Division of Calamba City. There was significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and teaching competence of the public-school teachers such as technical skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, technical skills and learning environment and diversity of learners, human skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, human skills and learning environment and diversity of learners, human skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, conceptual skills and learning environment and diversity of learners, conceptual skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, communication skills and learning environment and diversity of learners, supervisory skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, supervisory skills and learning environment and diversity of learners and supervisory skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting. The probability values were lesser than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. There was no significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and teaching competence of the public-school teachers in terms of technical skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting , technical skills and personal growth and professional development, human skills and personal growth and professional development, conceptual skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, conceptual skills and personal growth and professional development, communication skills and content knowledge and pedagogy, communication skills and curriculum planning and assessment & reporting, communication skills and personal growth and professional development, and supervisory skills, and personal growth and development. The probability values were greater than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.
6. Test of Significant Relationship between the Strategic Management Skills of the School Heads and Academic Readiness of the Public Schools in Cluster 4 District Division of Calamba City There was a significant relationship between the strategic management skills of the school heads and academic readiness of public schools as shown in the probability values were all 0.000 which was less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.
7. The Proposed Program
The program Project ASBSS: Attain Strong Bond for School Success is a strategic intervention on fostering healthy relationship between school head, teachers and school for the success of the school goals and objectives. This study assessed the challenges affecting the academic performance of Grade 9 Students in Horticultural Crop Production of Lopez West district. The findings of the study were used in crafting intervention materials. The mean was used to identify the extent of agreement of the respondents with the different indicators. The study has found the following significant findings:

Conclusions

Based on the data gathered and discussed the following conclusions were derived:

1. That the Cluster 4 School Heads demonstrated outstanding strategic management strategies that have a substantial impact on the overall performance and effectiveness of a school. The findings suggest that educational administrators who possess advanced strategic management skills are more capable of effectively addressing the intricate difficulties they face inside the educational system.
2. That the Teachers in Cluster 4 of public schools exhibit evident competence in their specific teaching domains, displaying the necessary knowledge, skills, and characteristics to provide exceptional education to their pupils. Furthermore, this study revealed that public school teachers exhibit a great commitment to their work. They engage in reflective activities, actively seek opportunities for self-improvement, and have genuine excitement for the teaching and learning process. Through their dedication to ongoing learning, they guarantee they stay up-to-date with the latest educational research and successful techniques, enabling them to provide an excellent education to their students.
3. That public schools in Cluster 4 possess the necessary academic readiness to effectively address the educational requirements of students. By analyzing indicators, it becomes clear that public schools have the essential resources, teaching techniques, and support structures required to offer kids a high-quality education. The academic readiness of public schools is influenced by the presence of proficient school heads, competent teachers, well craft curriculum, conducive learning environments, and active community involvement.
4. That there is clear evidence of contrasting perspectives between these two groups within the educational system. The differences in assessment may arise from variances in duties, responsibilities, and attitudes between school leaders and instructors in the educational system. Recognizing and addressing these conflicting opinions is essential for promoting collaboration, common knowledge, and successful decision-making within schools.
5. That effective strategic management skills by school heads in Cluster 4 positively influences the competence of their teachers within the educational system in some abovementioned indicators. School heads with proficient strategic management abilities guarantee that the curriculum, resources, and support systems are in harmony with the overarching vision and objectives of the school. This alignment fosters a cohesive and uniform educational experience for teachers, empowering them to efficiently execute instructional tactics and enhance student learning.
6. That the school leaders in Cluster 4 set a clear and deliberate course of action that has significant impact on the academic competence and readiness of schools. They created a plan for the entire school community to adhere to, guaranteeing that all endeavors focus on attaining academic preparedness. Educational administrators who possess strategic management abilities foster a constructive and cooperative educational environment. They establish an environment that fosters and sustains the growth, cooperation, and originality of teachers. Principals

enable instructors to improve their instructional methods, apply effective teaching methodologies, and continuously improve their competency by offering professional growth opportunities. Consequently, this has a beneficial impact on students' academic preparedness.

7. That the program, Project ASBSS is needed since it offers a comprehensive plan to improve and establish an effective relationship between school heads, teachers, and the school. The objective of this program is to establish a comprehensive and all-encompassing educational setting that promotes the achievement of students

Recommendations

Based on the data gathered and discussed the following recommendations were proposed:

1. School principals are advised to engage in self-reflection over their performance, actively seek criticism, and derive valuable lessons from both their achievements and setbacks coming from their heads and school community.
2. Develop a comprehensive strategy that delineates the school's overarching aspirations, specific targets, and the means by which they can be accomplished. Regularly reviewing and updating the plan is necessary to stay abreast of any changes. Finally, it is imperative to examine the school's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in order to develop impactful strategies.
3. Teachers are encouraged to actively pursue professional development options that are pertinent to their subject areas and specific teaching circumstances in order to improve their teaching skills. These development opportunities might manifest in diverse formats, including workshops, seminars, conferences, webinars, or even online courses.
4. Teachers should establish individual professional development plans (IPDPs) that correspond with their distinct requirements and objectives. By actively pursuing these possibilities, teachers can continuously enhance and refine their skills, ultimately resulting in significant advantages for their students and the educational community at large.
5. School should establish a distinct and persuasive vision and mission that establishes rigorous academic standards aligned with their School Improvement Plan (SIP). Additionally, the school should ensure that the curriculum is aligned with academic standards and learning objectives, promote effective teaching methods, provide continuous professional development opportunities, foster a supportive and inclusive school environment, encourage collaboration and professional learning communities, and cultivate a culture of continuous improvement through ongoing reflection, evaluation, and innovation.
6. Proposed a school program that can foster and build much stronger relationships between principals and teachers. This can be achieved by working together effectively, establishing clear communication channels,

- collaborating on projects and initiatives, and prioritizing mutual respect and understanding. By doing so, the school can become a true community of learners, where everyone is invested in each other's success.
7. Collaborate for various programs that enhance and develop the relationships between all the personnel involved in the school community.
 8. And lastly, for future researchers, they must adopt and consider this study to include diverse locales and incorporate variables beyond the ones mentioned in this study. It will broaden our understanding of the subject and uncover new findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adheres to the ethical guidelines set forth by the ethics committee or relevant body and complies with applicable laws and regulations. Ethical considerations were paramount throughout the design and execution of the study, and steps were taken to minimize any potential risks or harms to participants.

Informed Consent

Before participating, all individuals involved in the study were fully informed of the research aims, procedures, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. They were assured that participation was voluntary, and they could withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. The confidentiality of the participants' data was guaranteed, and identifying information was not collected.

Confidentiality and Data Protection

All data collected during the study were treated with the highest level of confidentiality. The information was anonymized and stored securely in accordance with the data protection regulations. Only authorized research team members had access to the data, and the data will be kept for the duration of the research and subsequent analysis period, after which it will be permanently deleted.

Ethical Approval

This research was approved by the school committee. The study protocol and research methods were reviewed to ensure that they met ethical standards and the rights of participants were safeguarded.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest related to this research. No financial or personal relationships influenced the study's design, data collection, analysis, or reporting.

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